

Determinants of the Intention to Leave among Public Sector Physicians in Morocco: Proposal for a Research Model

Les déterminants de l'intention de quitter chez les médecins du secteur public au Maroc : proposition d'un modèle de recherche

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Abstract:

This article highlights the worrying phenomenon of the mass exodus of doctors from the public sector, who find themselves forced to leave their posts either to join the private sector or to reinforce other countries with medical skills, thereby exacerbating the shortage of human resources in health and further disrupting the operation of public healthcare services. Our aim is, firstly, to propose a theoretical model identifying the factors most likely to influence the intention to leave and, secondly, to examine conceptually the mediating role of organizational commitment in this relationship. To this end, we mobilize social exchange theory, the organizational commitment model, and the theory of planned behavior to build our theoretical model on the antecedents of intention to leave and, consequently, voluntary turnover behaviors among public sector physicians. Our goal is to serve as a reference for further studies and contribute to the reflection on mechanisms that may curb the drain of medical skills from this crucial sector for public health in Morocco and across the globe.

Keywords: Intention to leave; tangible and intangible rewards; organizational commitment; public healthcare.

Résumé :

Cet article met en lumière le phénomène préoccupant de l'exode massif des médecins du secteur public qui se voient contraints de quitter leurs postes soit pour rejoindre le secteur privé ou pour renforcer d'autres pays en compétences médicales, ce qui aggrave la pénurie des ressources humaines sanitaires et perturbe davantage le fonctionnement des services de soins publics. Notre objectif consiste, d'une part, à proposer un modèle théorique identifiant les facteurs les plus susceptibles d'influencer l'intention de quitter et, d'autre part, à examiner conceptuellement le rôle médiateur de l'engagement organisationnel dans cette relation. Pour ce faire, nous mobilisons la théorie de l'échange social, le modèle de l'engagement organisationnel et la théorie du comportement planifié pour la construction de notre modèle théorique sur les antécédents de l'intention de quitter et, par conséquent, les comportements de roulement volontaire chez les médecins du secteur public, dans le but de servir de référence pour les études ultérieures et de contribuer à la réflexion sur les mécanismes pouvant freiner la fuite des compétences médicales de ce secteur crucial pour la santé publique au Maroc et dans le monde entier.

Mots clés : Intention de quitter; rémunération tangible et intangible; engagement organisationnel; santé publique.

Introduction

In a post-Covid-19 context, the public health sector, both nationally and internationally, has been experiencing a growing wave of resignations in recent years, which are affecting healthcare delivery and patient health (De Vries et al., 2023; Seathu Raman et al., 2024; Zarei et al., 2024). In response to this situation, compensation is seen as a key tool for retaining and attracting doctors. However, the traditional approach to compensation, which focuses solely on salary, bonuses, and benefits, is increasingly inadequate, and the importance of non-salary benefits has grown in recent years, especially with the arrival of new generations in the labor market (Pauget & Dammak, 2012). In this sense, the topic of intangible compensation is now an emerging subject in the scientific literature, attracting the attention of both researchers (Frimousse & Peretti, 2024) and managers, as it can contribute to employee retention through a new approach that includes both tangible and intangible compensation (Hallée et al., 2021). In the Moroccan context, the public health sector, which aims to be modern and efficient in light of major health reforms (Hassani & El Moussali, 2020), is facing a massive labor shortage exacerbated by the mass exodus of doctors and healthcare professionals (CNDH, 2022; Benabdallah & Chekrouni, 2023), which hinders the proper functioning of public health services and negatively impacts the quality of care (Estryn-Behar et al., 2010). Additionally, the public sector no longer attracts medical students, who prefer to pursue more promising opportunities abroad or in the private sector. Indeed, according to a study published by AK Sylla et al. (2021), 70.1% of final-year medical students planned to leave Morocco after graduation, seeking better working conditions and more attractive career prospects. It is therefore necessary to offer a competitive and attractive package of benefits that combines both tangible and intangible elements, capable of strengthening doctors' organizational commitment and retaining them in the public sector.

These alarming findings have motivated our ambition to contribute to the existing body of research on this subject by focusing on public sector physicians. In this regard, our article aims to propose a research model based on a literature review, a solid theoretical framework, and previous studies, to present a hypothetical model that can explain the determinants of the intention to leave among public sector physicians in Morocco. Based on this, we formulate the following research question:

What are the key determinants of the intention to leave among public sector physicians in Morocco?

At this point, our work presents a dual interest: at the theoretical level, it aims to enrich the scientific literature on staff retention. To this end, this article aims to propose a research model that can serve as a reference for future research on this subject. From a managerial perspective, this work aims to encourage public health sector managers to reflect on structuring HR policies to address the challenges of retaining and attracting doctors in Morocco's public sector.

To answer our research question, we will present the conceptual and theoretical framework of our subject. Then, we will present our research model as well as the resulting hypotheses. Finally, we will discuss the contributions of our model and propose some avenues for future research.

1. Conceptual Framework:

The intention to leave is defined as the conscious desire felt by the employee to leave the company. Several empirical studies have confirmed that the intention to leave and the voluntary act of leaving are positively linked (Bothma & Roodt, 2013; Cohen et al., 2016). Given that it is an important predictor of employee turnover, particularly voluntary turnover resulting from intention rather than life circumstances, many researchers have focused on studying employees' intention to leave and the factors that drive them to develop such an intention, which ultimately leads to their departure from the organization.

According to scientific literature, the factors influencing the intention to leave are numerous. However, compensation remains a key factor that has been extensively studied and confirmed by subsequent research (Hallée et al., 2021; St-Onge & Thériault, 2020; Milkovich et al., 2017). Overall compensation is divided into two main categories: tangible benefits (direct and indirect compensation) and intangible benefits (non-monetary compensation). Tangible compensation is further divided into direct and indirect compensation. Direct compensation refers to all the monetary amounts received directly by the employee. Indirect compensation refers to compensation that is not paid in cash but still incurs a cost for the employer (St-Onge & Thériault, 2020; Hallée et al., 2021). It represents the transactional financial rewards an employee can receive in exchange for work, whether paid directly, indirectly, or variably, in the short, medium, or long term. In their research, Renaud et al. (2016) include the following elements in tangible compensation: "base salary, bonuses, overtime pay, stock purchase programs, commission plans, benefits, insurance, additional benefits, vacations, absences, parental leave, pension plans, and any other form of transactional financial reward." Our study will focus on salary and benefits, which constitute the two main components of tangible

compensation and have been confirmed by previous studies as key determinants of the intention to leave the organization.

On the other hand, intangible compensation represents the beneficial non-monetary relational rewards that an employee can receive in exchange for work. These include work schedules, recognition, autonomy, promotions, challenges, good relationships with colleagues and immediate supervisors, communication, happiness at work, and any other form of beneficial non-monetary relational reward (Renaud et al., 2016). A more recent definition proposed by Côté & Renaud (2022) describes it as follows: "the set of actions taken by an employer to create intrinsic added value for the employee, for which there may be a monetary cost related to the creation of that value. This definition includes elements such as recognition, training and development, work-life balance, work environment, stimulating work, and many others."

In our study, which focuses on the context of the public health sector characterized by high demands and often challenging working conditions, we will concentrate on four components of intangible compensation, namely working conditions, work-family balance, training and development, and recognition. These variables have been confirmed in the literature as significant predictors of the intention to leave (Bennani & Bertal, 2019; Hewko et al., 2015; Noor, K. M., 2011; Renaud et al., 2021; Rubenstein et al., 2018).

2. Theoretical Framework:

Several theories have been developed around our research topic. Among these main theories, we present those we find most relevant and that we will use in our research model, namely the Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), and the Organizational Commitment Model (Meyer & Allen, 1991).

2.1 Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964)

The Social Exchange Theory, developed by Peter Blau in 1964, posits that there are exchange relationships between employees and their employers, where each party seeks to maximize their employment relationship. There are different types of exchange. The voluntary exchange of resources involves offering employees monetary benefits (salary increases, promotions, etc.) in exchange for a current or future service for the company, or also offering non-monetary and more relational benefits. Thus, the relationship between an employee and their employer constitutes a form of social exchange that comes with an expectation of reciprocity. According

to this theory, unmet professional expectations affect employees' behavior. Indeed, according to Blau's theory (1964), there is an intrinsic component to all social associations; that is, the employee providing a service expects to receive something in return for this transaction, which goes beyond the mere economic aspect. The absence of contractual empirical support regarding these intrinsic rewards presupposes that the employee knows what they want but is unsure of what they will receive. The theoretical framework of the psychological contract supports the nature of the relationship between an employer and their employees. This aligns with the Social Exchange Theory because the nature of the contract is not specified but emerges from the parties' expectations.

2.2 Organizational Commitment Model (Meyer & Allen, 1991)

Allen and Meyer defined organizational commitment as "a psychological bond between the employee and their organization, making it less likely that the employee will voluntarily leave the organization" (Allen & Meyer, 1990). Allen and Meyer first identified two dimensions of organizational commitment: affective attachment and financial attachment. After further research, Meyer and Allen identified another dimension, that of obligation. The three distinct components of organizational commitment identified by Meyer and Allen are as follows:

- **Affective commitment**, which is the emotional component of organizational commitment, refers to an employee continuing to work for an organization due to their emotional attachment, involvement, and identification with that organization (Allen & Meyer, 1990).
- **Continuance commitment**, which refers to commitment based on the cost associated with leaving a specific organization. The potential cost of leaving an organization includes the threat of losing time and effort invested in acquiring non-transferable skills, the loss of attractive benefits, the forfeiture of seniority privileges, or the obligation to uproot the family and disrupt personal relationships.
- **Normative commitment**, which refers to the perceived obligation of the employee to remain within the organization or to reflect the feeling of obligation to continue employment with an organization.

2.3 Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991)

The Theory of Planned Behavior is an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980). It is illustrated by a model comprising three variables that influence intention and, consequently, behavior, namely: individual attitudes toward behavior, perceived subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, which is the main contribution of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) compared to alternative theories in behavior adoption. This added variable accounts for situations where individuals are determined to adopt a certain behavior but are prevented from doing so due to a lack of confidence or control over the behavior in question (Ajzen, 1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior posits that individual intention is a crucial element in triggering behavior. This theory is particularly valued for its simple structure, clarity, and applicability across various fields. It has been frequently used by many researchers to examine a wide range of behaviors in different disciplines, such as health, marketing, entrepreneurship, and psychology. Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) assert that this model can explain almost all human behavior. The simplicity and parsimony of the Theory of Planned Behavior facilitate its application to a variety of behaviors. For this reason, since its introduction, TPB has remained one of the predominant theories in analyzing behavioral decision-making and studying the links between attitudes and behaviors, thus confirming its predictive potential and, in some cases, its explanatory capacity. Figure 1 below illustrates the variables of this theory and the interactions that arise from it.

Figure n°1: Model depicting the theory of planned behavior

Source : (Ajzen, 1991)

3. Proposed Research Model

Based on our theoretical framework and considering previous studies, we propose to formulate the following six main hypotheses to attempt to answer our research question. Following our literature review, we identified the most predictive and explanatory variables of turnover intention, which have already been empirically confirmed by recent studies in other contexts. Indeed, several previous studies (Noor, K. M. 2011; Nouwou, 2022; Côté & Renaud, 2022; Renaud, S., Saint-Onge, S. & Morin, L., 2021) have confirmed the important role of tangible and intangible compensation in reducing turnover intention. Therefore, considering the social exchange theory (Blau, 1964) and previous studies, we deemed it relevant to examine the impact of the components of tangible and intangible compensation on the turnover intention among public sector physicians through the following two hypotheses:

H1: The components of tangible compensation would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.

- **H1.1:** Salary would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.
- **H1.2:** Social benefits would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.

H2: The components of intangible compensation have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.

- **H2.1:** The work environment would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.
- **H2.2:** Recognition would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.
- **H2.3:** Training and development would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.
- **H2.4:** Work-life balance would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.

Based on the first meta-analysis on turnover intention in the public sector, titled "*What makes public employees want to leave their job? A meta-analysis of turnover intention predictors among public sector employees*" (Hur & Abner, 2023), which confirmed that affective organizational commitment is among the strongest predictors of turnover intention, and

according to the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991), which states that decisions preceding a given behavior result from a cognitive and emotional process in which behavior is indirectly influenced by attitude, it seems pertinent to us to study the mediating role of affective organizational commitment as an attitude in the relationship between tangible and intangible compensation and turnover intention.

H3: Affective organizational commitment as an attitude would play a mediating role in the relationship between tangible and intangible compensation and turnover intention among public sector physicians.

- **H3.1:** Affective organizational commitment mediates the relationship between salary and turnover intention among public sector physicians.
- **H3.2:** Affective organizational commitment mediates the relationship between social benefits and turnover intention among public sector physicians.
- **H3.3:** Affective organizational commitment mediates the relationship between the work environment and turnover intention among public sector physicians.
- **H3.4:** Affective organizational commitment mediates the relationship between recognition and turnover intention among public sector physicians.
- **H3.5:** Affective organizational commitment mediates the relationship between training and development and turnover intention among public sector physicians.
- **H3.6:** Affective organizational commitment mediates the relationship between work-life balance and turnover intention among public sector physicians.

The theoretical model of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991) also posits that social norms have a direct impact on attitude, and according to previous studies, relationships with both supervisors and colleagues have a significant impact on organizational commitment (Paillé, 2009).

H4: Immediate supervisor support and colleague support, as subjective norms, would have a positive impact on affective organizational commitment among public sector physicians.

- **H4.1:** Immediate supervisor support would have a positive impact on affective organizational commitment among public sector physicians.
- **H4.2:** Colleague support would have a positive impact on affective organizational commitment among public sector physicians.

According to Ajzen (1991), subjective norms correspond to the social pressure perceived by an individual regarding their behavior, based on the individual's beliefs about the expectations of

relevant reference groups. In his study, Paillé, P. (2009) confirmed that relationships with supervisors and colleagues have a negative impact on turnover intention in the organization. Therefore, we retain immediate supervisor support and colleague support as subjective norms within our research model, leading us to propose the following hypothesis:

H5: Immediate supervisor support and colleague support, as subjective norms, would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.

- **H5.1:** Immediate supervisor support would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.
- **H5.2:** Colleague support would have a negative impact on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.

According to Ajzen's theory (1991), perceived behavioral control represents the perception of ease or difficulty in performing a specific behavior. This third variable in the theory of planned behavior is determined by facilitating conditions, which refer to the availability or absence of necessary resources. The more individuals feel capable of accessing these resources, seizing opportunities, and overcoming anticipated obstacles, the more they will have a sense of control over the behavior, which will have a positive impact on their intention. Conversely, if they perceive an inability to execute the behavior in question, it will have a negative effect on their intention (Ajzen, 1991), hence the following proposition:

H6: External employment opportunities as a means of perceived behavioral control would have a negative effect on the turnover intention of public sector physicians.

Considering the previously stated hypotheses, we present below our theoretical research model.

Figure n°2: Theoretical research model

Source: Authors

Conclusion, Limitations, and Perspectives

In this article, we presented a proposal for a theoretical research model based on a literature review aimed at studying the determinants of turnover intention among public sector physicians in Morocco.

Our study highlights the crucial role that tangible and intangible compensation can play in turnover intention among public health sector physicians in Morocco, as well as the mediating role of affective organizational commitment in this relationship.

The contributions of our article are scientific, relying on a combination of three solid and foundational theories: the social exchange theory (Blau, 1964), the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991), and the organizational commitment model (Meyer & Allen, 1991). This combination provides a deepened and broadened perspective on the antecedents of the concept of turnover intention. At this stage, to our knowledge, no research has applied this theoretical combination in the context of our study.

Indeed, this model proposes a multidimensional analysis of the factors influencing turnover intention among public sector physicians, focusing on the central role of the components of tangible and intangible compensation, as well as the mediating role of affective organizational commitment as an attitude. Additionally, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control are included for a better understanding of this issue.

From a managerial standpoint, this article sheds light on a critical issue for the public health sector—namely, the massive turnover of public sector physicians—and aims to provoke reflection among managers on the factors contributing to excessive departures and the adoption of HR policies that could curb this medical turnover.

However, the main limitations of this research lie primarily in the fact that it offers only a theoretical contribution, as we have not yet empirically tested the proposed model. This limitation is explained by the fact that this work is part of a doctoral study that aims, in the next stage, to enrich and refine this research model through a qualitative exploratory study, followed by a confirmatory quantitative study among public sector physicians. The goal is to address our research hypotheses, which aim to reduce actual turnover behavior and ensure sustainable human resource management in Morocco's public health sector.

Regarding future research perspectives, our model has focused primarily on organizational factors to explore their influence on turnover behavior through turnover intention. However, other personal and social factors may also affect turnover intention. Thus, additional moderating variables that could explain more comprehensively the link between turnover intention and its explanatory variables may be added to this model to better predict this concept. Furthermore, this model could be tested through empirical studies in other contexts, and other variables could be studied with the same factors, such as quiet quitting, burnout, and organizational performance, to contribute to a more global vision of human resource management.

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